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POLICY BRIEF

SECURITY CHALLENGES IN A CYBER SOCIETY

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Why does cybersecurity require joint action for the stability of international policies? Geopolitical disputes over cyberspace control have grown, accentuating the difficulty of formulating universal definitions and standards, combined with the scarcity of regulations and laws. Cybersecurity is essential to ensure the full functioning of the current information society because the increased exposure and use of technologies, in both public and private matters, facilitates many processes of innovation and progress, accompanied by risks that may compromise the development of the poorest countries, and also being among the main challenges accessibility and common jurisdictional specificities.

Given the increased exposure and use of technologies, in both public and private matters, the cybersecurity context requires global cooperation to ensure its sustainable operation. Cyberattacks are considered dangerous to democracies and economies, while cyberspace participates in and interferes with the dynamics of political and social transformation, inside and outside the internet networks. Therefore, it is necessary to assume the reality of the complex interdependence of the international system, with multiple actors and connected events, in a volatile anarchy of relations between states and political transition.

Cyberspace facilitates many processes of innovation and progress, accompanied by risks that can compromise developing countries, with accessibility being among the main challenges. For financial reasons, poorer actors are looking for cheaper options and solutions, often below the recommended security requirements. Cybersecurity has become one of the main concerns among these actors, whose poor defensive capacity and insecure networks make them targets for cybercriminals, serving as a field of preparation for criminals to do more intense attacks. Since cyberspace runs parallel to the rest of the world, developed countries have an interest in exploiting and dominating it in order to gain sovereignty and influence over their rivals, generating dependence on developing countries to protect their information

(...) We recommend that policymakers consider the joint action of stakeholders and the multiplicity of mechanisms as a response to crimes, since there is no simple and individualized solution to contingency problems that are in constant technical and paradigm evolution. (...)

In addition, there are common jurisdictional specificities as challenges to be overcome since cybercrime presents new dilemmas for conflict resolution and interconnected defense mechanisms. As individual defenses are more vulnerable to updated and strengthened cybercrimes, which are constantly being improved, there are still difficulties in the international legal sphere for the common definition of the criminal, the place of the crime, the crime, and the victim, in order to then prosecute cybercrimes, as they involve jurisdictions of different countries, as well as changing domestic policies and governments.

Cybercrimes are damaging to all actors in the international system, where problems in a national territory can become the subject of global discussion. We recommend that policymakers consider the joint action of stakeholders and the multiplicity of mechanisms as a response to crimes, since there is no simple and individualized solution to contingency problems that are in constant technical and paradigm evolution. Bringing together actors from civil society, the private and public sectors, academia, and technical experts will strengthen cybersecurity and improve effective and legal crime resolutions.

About the Author

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